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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL
INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

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The operational guidelines describe the services of the Research and Innovation Support Group (R&I SG) that are available to ENLIGHT partners.

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INTRODUCTION

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Research and Innovation Support Group (R&I SG) operational guidelines and service offer describe the services that are available to ENLIGHT partners and the research and innovation community.

This report aims at formalizing the creation of the Research and Innovation Support Group of the ENLIGHT alliance, presenting the services the group offers to the ENLIGHT community. It summarizes the way the group operates.

The first section is dedicated to the R&I SG. It details what the R&I SG is; its composition and its objectives.

The second section deals with the services the R&I SG offers to the ENLIGHT Research and Innovation community to support in building up competitive European and international research and innovation projects.

Finally, the third section describes the guidelines for the R&I SG operation. It highlights some general principles and internal communication processes as well as the tasks and responsibilities of the R&I SG members.

1. THE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION SUPPORT GROUP (R&I SG)

WHAT IS IT?

The R&I SG is a virtual working group of research support officers from the nine ENLIGHT partners who support the ENLIGHT community on European and international research and innovation proposals/projects. Each partner allocates staff to participate in the R&I SG.

Grant officers at the University of Tartu, the University of Groningen and the University of Bordeaux coordinate it.

The R&I SG will exist until the last joint European or international research project with ENLIGHT label is finalised.

COMPOSITION

The R&I SG is composed of grant officers from the Research Support Offices (RSO) of the nine ENLIGHT partners to support the ENLIGHT RISE community to set up European and international proposals/projects.

The R&I SG is a close-knit group composed of max. two representatives per partner. The 9 ENLIGHT partners aim at ensuring continuity and avoiding turnover in the R&I SG.

It is expected to tend to gender-balance and ensure equal representation between partners.

The R&I SG will be composed of research support staff who have different profiles: funding officers, research Funding advisers, Grant Consultants etc.

OBJECTIVES OF THE R&I SG

The R&I SG's main goal is to support the ENLIGHT community in developing joint competitive European and international research and innovation projects.

Its specific objectives are the following:

- Providing the ENLIGHT community with an easier and broader access to European /international funding opportunities.
- Identifying synergies that can be achieved in different sources of international & EC funding
- Facilitating and incentivizing research collaborations between ENLIGHT partners
- Identifying suitable funding support in response to the research idea
- Supporting the preparation of research and innovation proposals

The R&I-SG will work closely with the ENLIGHT RISE governance towards collaborative research projects of strategic interest for the network (see section 3).

It will also work in interaction with associated societal partners and external business partners through the ENLIGHT Regional Academies and Think Tank.

2. SERVICE OFFER

The R&I SG will provide the following support to the ENLIGHT RISE Community.

1. Dedicated monitoring & information service to the core groups/ pilot focus groups

The R&I SG will provide information on the calls for proposals that could be of interest for the ENLIGHT Pilot Focus Groups/ E+ Core Groups¹ and ENLIGHT researchers.

Two to three representatives of the R&I SG will participate in the Pilot Focus Groups/E+ Core Groups depending on the specialities of the R&I SG staff (focusing on specific topics and/or funding schemes) acting as “EU funding experts”.

The R&I SG will examine existing and forthcoming EU and other R&I funding opportunities to support the development of collaborative research project proposals based on the topics/interests of the Pilot Focus Groups/E+ Core Groups . The R&I SG will deliver specific presentations of EU R&I funding possibilities.

For proposals emerging from the Pilot Focus Groups/ E+ Core Groups, the R&I SG will also offer more services such as administrative support for submission and proof reading.

2. Partner search

The R&I SG members will act as facilitators to help researchers find partners in other ENLIGHT universities in order to initiate collaboration and build joint R&I proposals.

The R&I SG members will regularly exchange information on partner requests they are aware of. They are committed to relaying the R&I Partner search towards the scientific community from their universities that could match the profile/expertise sought for.

They will exchange information on expertise available at ENLIGHT partners and facilitate the establishment of contacts with potential partners.

The group will also promote the use of the partner search tool from the ENLIGHT Website ([Enlight Partner Search](#)) towards the scientific communities in the respective universities.

3. Information on incentive programmes

The R&I SG will inform on incentive programmes that are available for the ENLIGHT community (seed fundings, awards...).

4. Development of support kits and guides

¹ The ENLIGHT Pilot Focus Groups/E+ Core Groups are groups implemented in the frame of the ENLIGHT Alliance. The focus groups are composed of researchers who will coordinate the emergence and/or expansion of collaborative R&I actions within ENLIGHT. The Core Groups are composed of disciplinary experts, creative agents, who identify and refine teaching and learning formats for the ENLIGHT offer and initiate innovative learning opportunity formats.

The R&I SG will provide and develop support kits to the ENLIGHT R&I community. It will develop tools that will help ENLIGHT researchers to understand the European Commission's expectations, calls specificities and facilitate the setting up of a proposal such as:

- an ENLIGHT template proposed to coordinators of ENLIGHT proposals; annotated guides for applicants
- guidelines on transversal issues
- one page brief per main Horizon Europe programme.

The tools will be available on SharePoint and upon request sent by email.

5. Information and organisation of joint events

The R&I SG will inform the whole community on events organised by the European Commission (infodays, brokerage events...) and relevant for the ENLIGHT domains.

The R&I SG will organise:

- info sessions & project idea pitch sessions focusing on EU R&I funding programmes relevant for the flagship domains
- trainings/workshops on transversal topics relevant for any call application and in cooperation with other ENLIGHT RISE WP leaders (e.g. gender/open access, impact, science with society...).

All researchers from all partners will have possibility to attend the different events, held online and, whenever possible recorded so as to be incorporated in the toolkits.

6. Promotion of the digital matching tool

As part of ENLIGHT RISE, the University of Tartu will develop a digital matching tool, which will facilitate the matching between researchers and funding and between researchers from the ENLIGHT alliance. The R&I SG will introduce the tool to the ENLIGHT researchers and will promote its use.

3. OPERATIONAL GUIDELINES

3.1 General principles

The R&I SG is composed of two persons per institution maximum (1+ 1 substitute).

The R&I SG will determine with the PBM and the Governing Board the criteria for proposals to be considered as strategic for ENLIGHT.

Two to three members of the R&I SG will monitor each pilot focus group/E+ Core Group ensuring the involvement of each ENLIGHT partner.

Each member of the R&I SG is free to propose any tool relevant to be shared with the community. However, prior sharing, each tool must be sent to the R&I SG for validation by consensus.

3.2 Meetings and internal communication

The R&I SG will inform regularly the PBM (three times per year) and the Governing Board (every 6 months) on proposals and collaborations that emerge. The R&I SG will produce a note once a year to the Governing Board for that purpose. It will also liaise with WP2 with regard to the initiatives of the Pilot Focus Groups.

The R&I SG will meet once a month virtually. The monthly WP1 meetings will be used for this. No extra meetings will be necessary.

All common documents to be provided to the Pilot Focus Groups and the ENLIGHT researcher community (i.e., commented guides/templates...) will be uploaded and centralised on the ENLIGHT RISE SharePoint according to the RISE Management Handbook.

For all tools (PowerPoint, templates...), the R&I SG shall apply the general principles defined in the ENLIGHT RISE Communication action plan strategy available on [SharePoint](#).

The R&I SG will monitor the setting up of proposals that involve several ENLIGHT partners via a shared file on joint submissions available on SharePoint.

3.3 R&I SG members' tasks and responsibilities

Being a member of the R&I SG confers some responsibilities.

The member of the R&I SG is the representative of its institution. As such, he/she is the main contact in case of partner search or any other request/need for information.

He/she shall liaise with his/her internal service to inform on the actions of the R&I SG. For specific identified proposal submissions, he/she liaises with the right people in his/her institution who could have the right expertise. He/she acts as an expert on a given programme/topics for other R&I SG members if needed.

In particular, the R&I SG members will be responsible for the following tasks:

- Participation in the R&I SG monthly meeting.
- Monitoring and participation in the Pilot Focus Groups/Core Groups' meetings they are in charge of
- Development of relevant tools (info days, annotated guides...) freely available to the ENLIGHT Researchers and the Pilot Focus Groups
- Provision of information on the calls for proposals/tools to the Pilot Focus Groups that might be of interest for the group
- Advising and monitoring of the R&I initiatives that emerge from the Pilot focus group they are in charge of
- Monitoring of the setting up of proposals that involve several ENLIGHT partners via a shared file on SharePoint
- Reporting to the WP1 co-leads on the different activities and proposals submitted.

CONCLUSION

This report intends to describe the functioning and the services the R&I SG offered to the research and innovation community of ENLIGHT. The services and tasks of the R&I SG will evolve through time depending on the needs of ENLIGHT's targets (researchers) and the vision of the Governing Board.